

Single-top production at the LHC

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Introduction

- Top is the heaviest particle known
- Life time $\sim 10^{-25}$ s:
 - no hadronisation, study the bare quark
- Decays almost exclusively to Wb
- **Golden** t-channel:
 - has the largest cross section
 - has the largest S/B
 - discovered at Tevatron 2009
 - observed at LHC 2011

- Tests of SM prediction:
 - cross section $\propto |V_{tb}|^2$
 - test CKM matrix unitarity
 - can constrain PDFs
- Probing new physics
 - charged heavy W' , H^+
 - access anomalous couplings
- Help tuning MC generators (unfolded distributions)

• Signatures:

- 1 isolated lepton
- E_T^{miss} from the neutrino
- 1 high P_T forward jet
- 1 high P_T b-tagged jet
- Neural network to enhance S/B
- Separate cross section determined for l^+ and l^- events

- Fiducial volume defined using stable particles selected with cuts very close to the final selection

$$\sigma_{\text{fid}} = \frac{N_{\text{fid}}}{N_{\text{sel}}} \cdot \frac{\hat{\nu}}{L_{\text{int}}} \quad \leftarrow \text{Measured number of signal events}$$

$$\sigma_{\text{fid.}}(tq) = 9.78 \pm 0.57 \text{ pb}$$

$$\sigma_{\text{fid.}}(\bar{t}q) = 5.77 \pm 0.45 \text{ pb}$$

- Fiducial cross section reduces systematic uncertainties of MC generators
- **Uncertainties:** dominated by systematics: jet energy scale, NLO matching choice and lepton reconstruction

t-channel at 8 TeV: total

Eur. Phys. J. C 77 (2017) 531

Fiducial cross section extrapolated to full phase space to measure the full cross section

$$\sigma_{\text{tot}} = \frac{N_{\text{tot}}}{N_{\text{fid}}} \cdot \sigma_{\text{fid}}$$

$$\sigma_{tq}^{\text{tot}} = 56.7^{+4.3}_{-3.8} \text{ pb}$$

$$\sigma_{\bar{t}q}^{\text{tot}} = 32.9^{+3.0}_{-2.7} \text{ pb}$$

$$R_t = \frac{\sigma_{tq}}{\sigma_{\bar{t}q}} = 1.72 \pm 0.09$$

Total cross section using different MC generators

- Without unitarity assumption
 $f_{LV} \cdot |V_{tb}| = 1.029 \pm 0.048$

- Left-handed form factor
- In the SM it is exactly 1

Select events with O_{NN} cut to enhance signal purity

Unfolded distributions:

- $P_T(t)$ and $y(t)$ for top and antitop at parton level
- $P_T(t)$, $|y(t)|$, $P_T(j)$, and $|y(j)|$ for top and antitop at particle level

Good agreement with the NLO predictions

t-channel at 13 TeV

CMS-PAS-TOP-17-011

- Signatures:
 - 1 isolated lepton (muon, electron)
 - P_{T}^{miss} and m_{T}^W cuts to suppress multi-jet backgrounds
 - high P_T forward jet
 - high P_T b-tagged jet
- 4 events categories according to number of jets and b-tagged jets (2j-0b, **2j-1b**, 3j-1b and 3j-2b)
- BDTs used to enhance S/B
 - trained in 2j-1b region separately for electron and muon channels
 - applied to the 2j-1b, 3j-1b, and 3j-2b categories, separately for the two different flavours and charges of the lepton
 - a maximum likelihood fit is performed simultaneously on the 12 different BDT output distributions

$$\sigma(tq) = 136.3 \pm 20.0 \text{ pb}$$

$$\sigma(\bar{t}q) = 82.7 \pm 13.1 \text{ pb}$$

$$\sigma(tq + \bar{t}q) = 219.0 \pm 33.1 \text{ pb}$$

t-channel at 13 TeV

CMS-PAS-TOP-17-011

JHEP 04 (2017) 086

$$R_t = 1.65 \pm 0.02(\text{stat}) \pm 0.04(\text{syst})$$

$$|f_{LV} V_{tb}| = 1.00 \pm 0.005(\text{exp}) \pm 0.02(\text{theo})$$

$$R_t = \frac{\sigma(tq)}{\sigma(\bar{t}q)} = 1.72 \pm 0.09(\text{stat.}) \pm 0.18(\text{syst.})$$

$$f_{LV} \cdot |V_{tb}| = 1.07 \pm 0.09$$

Signatures:

- 2 opposite sign isolated leptons
- E_T^{miss} from 2 neutrinos
- 1 high P_T b-tagged jet

- Signal and control regions defined according to number of jets and b-tagged jets
- BDT used to enhance S/B
- Binned maximum likelihood fit used to extract the cross section using signal and control regions

ATLAS: Observed (expected) significance **7.7σ** (6.9σ)

CMS: Observed (expected) significance **5.4σ** (6.1σ)

$|V_{tb}| = 1.03 \pm 0.12(\text{exp}) \pm 0.04(\text{th.})$

$|V_{tb}| = 1.01 \pm 0.10$

tW at 13 TeV

arXiv:1805.07399

Prefit

Postfit

Region	tW	t \bar{t}	tW	t \bar{t}
1j1b	6147 \pm 442	30622 \pm 1862	5440 \pm 604	30592 \pm 582
2j1b	3125 \pm 294	48484 \pm 1984	2888 \pm 321	47436 \pm 612
2j2b	725 \pm 85	25052 \pm 2411	719 \pm 88	25114 \pm 281

➔ Most contributing

Impressive precision!

$$\sigma(pp \rightarrow tW) = 63.1 \pm 1.8(\text{stat.}) \pm 6.4(\text{syst.}) \pm 2.1(\text{lumi})\text{fb}$$

Systematics uncertainties:

- Electron and muon efficiencies $\sim 3.2\%$
- Trigger efficiency 2.7%
- ttbar normalisation 2.8%

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@ATLAS: Inclusive measurement performed using 2015 data “ $\sim 30\%$ uncertainty”

- Apply a cut on the BDT to enhance the tW signal
- Cross section measured as a function of: $E(b)$, $m(l_1 b)$, $m(l_2 b)$, $E(l_1 b)$, $m_T(l_1 \nu b)$ and $m(l_1 b)$
- Top quark and W boson kinematics not directly accessible in dilepton channel, due to 2 neutrinos
- Measured cross sections are normalised to the fiducial cross section to reduce uncertainties

Results are in good agreement with predictions from several MC event generators

$$|\mathcal{A}_{Wtb}|^2 = |\mathcal{A}_{1R} + \mathcal{A}_{2R}|^2$$

$$= |\mathcal{A}_{2R}|^2 + |\mathcal{A}_{1R}|^2 + 2\text{Re}(\mathcal{A}_{1R}\mathcal{A}_{2R}^*)$$

ttbar

tW

interference

- ttbar and single top tW can have identical final state \rightarrow QM interference
- Simulations are to factorise ttbar and tW by one of two schemes:
 - diagram removal (**DR**) which removes the interference term explicitly
 - diagram subtraction (**DS**) which includes the interference but applies a cross-section level subtraction to remove the double counting
- The difference is considered as a theoretical uncertainty on single top modelling
 - can be large in phase spaces probed by searches
- Recent NLO calculation including proper treatment of the interference is available

- Unlike traditional tW analyses: target region where interference effect and DR/DS difference is large and try to measure it
- Use variable sensitive to these effects
- *Powheg-Box-Res* models full $m_{b\ell}^{\text{minimax}}$ well across the full distribution, and beyond the top-quark mass where DR/DS diverge

$$m_{b\ell}^{\text{minimax}} \equiv \min\{\max(m_{b_1\ell_1}, m_{b_2\ell_2}), \max(m_{b_1\ell_2}, m_{b_2\ell_1})\}$$

- Signatures:
 - 1 isolated lepton
 - E_T^{miss} from the neutrino
 - 2 high P_T b-tagged jet
- Many tricks to extract the signal
 - signal and control regions
 - MEM and BDT to enhance S/B

Systematics uncertainties:

- Background normalisation
- Jet energy scale
- MC statistics

• Observed significance is 3.2 (3.9) σ and 2.5 (1.1) σ for ATLAS and CMS experiments, respectively.

- It was hard at 8 TeV and it is harder at 13 TeV
 - worse S/B

Cross section summary

V_{tb} summary

- Measured total cross section is converted to V_{tb} measurements

$$|f_{LV} \cdot V_{tb}|^2 = \frac{\sigma_{\text{meas.}}}{\sigma_{\text{pred.}}}$$

- 5% precision achieved
- ATLAS and CMS combination in progress

Phys. Lett. B 780 (2018) 557

Phys. Lett. B 779 (2018) 358

- Electroweak process not observed so far (800 fb at 13 TeV)
- Sensitive to tZ and WWZ coupling
- First step on the way to tH measurement
- Trilepton channel is the most promising for first observation despite small BR (2.2%)

2015+2016 data

ATLAS

- 3 leptons (muon or electrons)
 - 2 opposite-sign leptons ± 10 GeV Z mass window
- 1 b-jet + forward jet
- Separate estimates of non-prompt lepton backgrounds
- Neural network is used to enhance S/B
- 1 SR is used in the fit

CMS

- 3 leptons (muon or electrons)
 - Z and Drell-Yan included
 - 2 opposite-sign leptons ± 15 GeV Z mass window
- 1 b-jet + 1 or 2 untagged jets
- Combined estimate of non-prompt lepton backgrounds
- BDT is used to enhance S/B
- 2 SR and 1 CR are used in the fit

Phys. Lett. B 780 (2018) 557

- The observed (expected) significance is **4.2σ (5.4σ)**

$$\sigma_{tZq} = 600 \pm 170(\text{stat.}) \pm 140(\text{syst.})\text{fb}$$

$$\sigma_{tZq} = 800 \text{ fb}_{-7.4}^{+6.1} \% \text{ theory}$$

Phys. Lett. B 779 (2018) 358

- The observed (expected) significance is **3.7σ (3.1σ)**

$$\sigma(pp \rightarrow tq \ell^+ \ell^-) \rightarrow 123_{-31}^{+33}(\text{stat.})_{-23}^{+29}(\text{syst.})\text{fb}$$

$$\sigma_{t\ell^+\ell^-q} = 94.2_{-1.8}^{+1.9}(\text{scale}) \pm 2.5(\text{PDF})\text{fb}$$

$t\gamma q$ at 13 TeV

arXiv:1808.02913

- 1 isolated muon $P_T > 26$ GeV
- 1 isolated photon $P_T > 25$ GeV
- $E_T^{\text{miss}} > 30$ GeV
- 2 jets with $P_T > 40$ GeV, $|\eta| < 4.7$
- 1 b-tagged jet

Process	Event yield
$t\bar{t} + \gamma$	1401 ± 131
$W\gamma + \text{jets}$	329 ± 78
$Z\gamma + \text{jets}$	232 ± 55
Misidentified photon	374 ± 74
$t\gamma$ (s- and tW-channel)	57 ± 8
$VV\gamma$	8 ± 3
Total background	2401 ± 178
Expected signal	154 ± 24
Total SM prediction	2555 ± 180
Data	2535

$t\gamma q$ at 13 TeV

arXiv:1808.02913

- BDT used to enhance S/B
 - 8 variables used in the training
- Binned maximum likelihood fit used to extract the cross section
- Full BDT in the SR and $t\bar{t}\gamma$ CR distributions are used in the fit
 - $t\bar{t}\gamma$ CR == 2 b-tagged jets
- The observed (expected) significance is **4.4 σ (3.0 σ)**
- The fiducial cross section

$$\sigma(pp \rightarrow t\gamma j) \cdot \mathcal{B}(t \rightarrow \mu\nu b) = 115 \pm 17(\text{stat}) \pm 30(\text{syst})\text{fb}$$

Dominant systematics:

- jet energy scale
- signal modelling
- $Z\gamma$ + jets normalisation

Summary

- Single top quark production processes are measured at different CME by ATLAS and CMS Collaborations
 - t-channel comprehensive measurements at 8 TeV, 13 TeV takes time
 - tW-channel is going differential
 - s-channel particularly challenging at 13 TeV
- ATLAS and CMS have evidence for the production of a single top quark in association with a Z boson at 13 TeV
 - discovery is on the horizon
- CMS has evidence for the production of a single top quark in association with a photon
- With the Full Run2 dataset, precision measurements, and rare single top quark processes can be investigated